

THE INFORMATION SOCIETY AND THE COGNITIVE LIMITS OF THE INDIVIDUAL:

Rethinking Social Stratification in the Age of Information Overload

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Abstract

The sharp leap in science and technology has given rise to a new state of human civilization, described as the 'information society.' Alongside the benefits of the unceasing flow of information exchanged through total communication, the negative consequences of 'information overload' have increasingly become apparent — both at the organizational and individual levels. Since it is not possible for the individual to self-isolate from this process, two options remain available: to develop automated protective mechanisms in the psyche, and/or to apply volitional effort in selecting the amount of information processed by consciousness.

Insofar as individuals are not identical, signs of a watershed are already clearly visible between the group of people who are able to exercise tighter control in the communication process and the group of those who succumb to the temptation to absorb information uncritically. Could this lead to a new principle of stratification in society?

Keywords: *information society; information overload; communication; psychology; psychographic profiles; stratification; sociology; cognitive limits; digital minimalism; social media addiction*

Introduction

The fundamentally new possibilities for producing and broadcasting enormous amounts of information, created at the end of the 20th century, placed the individual in a radically different situation compared to the preceding era of traditional communication. As a result of the ever-increasing means of creating and disseminating information — from economic, social, and cultural entities as well as from individuals themselves — accompanied by the rapid development of communication technology and systems, human beings found themselves in a cardinal new situation for which they had no prior experience.

The problem of overloading the communication field with mountains of information is historically relatively new (from the perspective of the entire period of civilization's existence), and — what is even more important — it has not frozen at some stable point but, on the contrary, is deepening further.

The information society is a phenomenon that arose as a result of the scientific and technological development of civilization. The immanent characteristics of this society lead to visible and unambiguous consequences at both the organizational and individual levels. Along with the undeniable benefits of increasing the volume of information and the means of its production and distribution, some clearly expressed negative consequences are categorically observed that create a problem for the individual. They arise from information overload, with which human civilization is confronted for the first time in its history.

The Concept of the 'Information Society'

The social result of the influx of information — thanks to the possibilities for its creation, replication, and dissemination — is the realization that society has graduated into a new type: an information society. This concept itself is a synthesis of the main characteristic of the fifth era of communication: that each individual, through the full complex of their valences originating from all their social roles, enters — as if into a synaptic structure — into contact with an unlimited number of other communicating units (individuals like themselves or structured subjects of the economy and social life in its overall, non-production-commercial sense).

What is essential here is to emphasize the individual's adoption of various social roles — their 'acting in different plays' — rather than viewing them through a monocle, because their functioning through these different roles leads to the exponential increase of the information they exchange. The combination of fundamentally new instruments for creating and disseminating information (computer technologies, software, the Internet, mobile communications) with the increasing degree of interconnections between all types of entities in society has immeasurably increased the amount of stored and consumed information, which has become a defining feature of modern society.

The birth of the concept of the 'information society' was not the result of years of research or 'heavy' academic discussions. It is considered that the Japanese version of the expression (joho shakai, johoka shakai) appeared in a conversation between the famous architect Kisho Kurokawa and the distinguished historian and anthropologist Tudao Umesao in 1961. In written form it appeared only 3 years later, in January 1964, as the title 'Sociology in Information Societies' of a study by Jiro Kamishima — though the title was not in fact his, but was given by editor Michiko Igarashi [1].

The theme of the complex complexity of the information society is gradually making its way and increasingly consolidating the opinions of researchers. If there is one thing none of them denies, it is the issue of the overloading of the individual's consciousness by the enormous amount of information and as a consequence of its unimaginable creation and distribution, permeating every moment of the lives of individuals and structured entities. Thus one arrives at a farewell to the past (the previous stages in the development of communication and

society) and entry into a fundamentally new stage in the existence of civilization: 'Information overload is characterized by growing dependence on appropriate, accurate information for survival and flourishing to a degree that is dramatic both in volume and in breadth... Taken together, all these changes represent a historical break from the past' [2].

Gradually, the 'information problem' went beyond the borders of individual states: it became institutionalized to the point of being the subject of discussions in the forum with the widest representation — the United Nations [3]. In this way, the information society effectively received planetary status. This does not mean, however, that its theoretical frameworks were fully outlined and universally accepted.

On the contrary: while unanimously accepting the axiomatic characteristics of the information society (volume, speed of dissemination, and total scope of information), experts are far from unanimous regarding basic characteristics of the interaction of subjects with information in the communication process, and the balance between the benefits and harms of the information flood.

Challenges of the Information Society

One of the greatest achievements of the fifth era of communication [4] is considered to be the freedom the individual gains to consume information in an almost unlimited quantity and to communicate with an unlimited number of addressees. But in every new era some new degree of freedom is achieved, which in turn becomes a new type of constraint. This is why, speaking of modern man, Fromm raises the question of the real nature of what from today's perspective appears as greater freedom: '...from freedom one moves to a new dependence' [5]. This statement was wittily transcribed in a cartoon depicting a demonstration of slaves in Rome, carrying a placard with the slogan 'Forward to the bright future of feudalism!'

In a relatively short period after the dawn of the electronic age, observers identified the nature of the problems and the instruments that generated them: 'As the role of information grows beyond everyone's expectations, it becomes too much. "TMI" (Too Much Information), people say now. We have information fatigue, anxiety and saturation. We have encountered the Devil of Information Overload' [6]. Unable to detach and distance themselves from information streams, individuals began forging the bars of their new cage with every presence on social networks, with every email, with following a news story across numerous sites and posts. What gradually began to emerge as the focus of analyses of this process was the creation of gigantic obstacles to the individual's ability to concentrate, due to the countless stimuli irritating their consciousness.

Of course, the thirst for more, more diverse and more accessible information has always accompanied the development of human civilization. But it has become increasingly clear that the benefits of access to an incredible amount of information have their reverse side: tension in the individual's mind, loss of direction, lower productivity of their consciousness. This leads one of the most resonant voices in the analysis of the information society to summarize: 'Distractions in our lives have been multiplying for a long time, but never has there been an environment that, like the web, has been programmed to spread our attention so widely and make it so insistent' [7].

We cannot grasp the scale of the change affecting each individual and civilization as a whole without acknowledging the deep character of the tremors in both the social fabric and the consciousness of the individual personality. Relatively early came warnings that excessive concentration on information and its delivery systems could divert attention from the fair availability and distribution of information's benefits [8].

Society does not function other than as the sum of the actions and interactions between individual agents and entities, and these actions now immanently contain within themselves the characteristics of the new communication era. One of these characteristics is the displacement of informational freedom from the prerogatives of the individual personality.

Electronic messages are the bars that now form their prison, into which they have voluntarily self-exiled. This new principle of existence inevitably affects cultural layers and the very functioning of the social fabric. For this reason, in all cases we are speaking of a gigantic, literally revolutionary leap — both in the consciousness of the individual and in society as a whole — and this change cannot be ignored: 'Quantitative changes in information create a qualitatively new type of social system, the information society' [9].

It is worth noting that in analyzing new realities, the concept of 'information society' is often used synonymously with 'network society': '...The information paradigm and the network society cause systemic disruptions in the sequential order of phenomena' [10]. The concept of 'networkedness' — beyond mere 'informedness' — creates a considerably deeper picture of society and better explains the real order of difficulties the individual experiences in the flow of information exchange and reception.

'Networkedness' implies a higher level of information consumption, since each individual or entity comes into contact with an enormous number of other individuals or entities. This better explains information overload and the need to find mechanisms to cope with it. To a large degree, this can be connected to the possibilities of control — or the impossibility of control. Early in the digital era, experts warned that between 'broadcasters' of information and 'receivers' of information an obvious dissonance is built in terms of control over communication, visible even in a single segment such as email: 'The email system, if used by many people, can cause serious problems through information overload. The reason for this problem is that it is so easy to send a message to a large number of people, and that systems are often designed to give the sender too much control over the communication process and the receiver too little' [11].

This conclusion underlines a fundamental characteristic of the information society and of the information overload it generates: the addressee of the information generated by someone becomes increasingly helpless in the communication process. They are unable to 'plug their ears' or stop the onslaught of the countless molecules of information attacking them from all sides, created by ever more insistent 'broadcasters.' The paradox, however, is that the 'victim' of information voluntarily accelerates this process, obediently giving in to the temptations with which it seduces them.

The Impact of Information Overload on the Individual

The information burden falls on the individual through two vectors: the first — through information they did not seek, did not desire, but which mercilessly overtakes them. The second vector concerns their personal volitional efforts to produce, share, and consume information. Data from global surveys show that in 2022, with a world population of 7.91 billion, Internet users numbered 4.95 billion (62.6% of all inhabitants of the Earth), while active users of social networks reached 4.62 billion (58.4% of all). Even more impressive are the data on the average daily time an individual spends in this boundless information field: 6 hours and 58 minutes on the Internet overall, of which 2 hours and 27 minutes specifically on social networks [12]. It must be explicitly noted that the trend registered by these regular surveys is unrelenting: a univocal increase both in the absolute number of users and in the time they devote to this information.

The fundamentally new condition in which the avalanche of information placed the human individual could not fail to attract the attention of researchers, who very quickly sharpened their focus on the consequences of its impact. What was common to the results, assessments, and analyses obtained was a clustering of worrying opinions in which negative context began to predominate. In practice, the spotlight fell on the fact that the overproduction of information began inexorably to exhaust one of the most precious resources for a person — the time they have available, which is ultimately absolutely limited [13]. At the same time, the connection between the decisions the individual is literally required to make every minute at all levels of

their existence — in all their social roles — and the burden of information was clearly formulated.

In the task/solution aspect, the following definitions of information overload emerged: 'Information overload is a condition in which a decision maker is faced with a set of information (i.e., information load with information characteristics such as quantity, complexity, and level of redundancy, contradiction, and inconsistency) involving the accumulation of discrete information signals of varying size and complexity that impede the decision maker's ability to optimally determine the best possible decision' [14]. Insofar as the individual is placed in a constant need to make all kinds of decisions, this formulation actually raised the question of how well it is possible to make good decisions under conditions of information overload — and thus directed the spotlight toward the worrying decline in the individual's ability to function normally and adequately when 'drowned' in information.

Researchers are categorical about how information overload occurs and what consequences it leads to for the individual: 'Information overload occurs when the volume of information offered exceeds the limited human capacity to process information. The result is dysfunctional effects such as stress and confusion' [15].

In a concise form, the concept of information overload can be presented as the relationship between the amount of information consumed and the individual's capacity to process it, relative to the time objectively available for carrying out this process — with cases of incommensurability of these quantities leading to adverse consequences for the individual.

According to a growing number of researchers, the resultant of information overload is markedly unfavorable for the individual: 'The consequences of information overload for the average information user are almost always negative. They have to face a whole set of challenges to find the information they need, which leads to fatigue and anxiety' [16].

The fundamental problem with information overload is that it is not a one-time event occurring in some strictly defined period of time. The thesis around which most authors agree is that information overload permeates every moment of daily life and every human activity. In the vast majority of cases, they draw attention no longer so much to the benefits as to the negative consequences of the production and dissemination of an unimaginable volume of information. The essential point is that these negative consequences are examined not only at the level of society as a whole, but — quite rightly — are interpreted from the perspective of the individual and their own psychology: 'Numerous psychological and economic consequences of information overload lead to serious consequences at both individual and organizational levels' [17].

The complexity and multidimensionality of the problem have been noted by researchers who observe the various elements pervading information overload: 'Information overload is related to many neighboring constructs such as cognitive overload, sensory overload, communication overload, knowledge overload, and information fatigue syndrome' [18]. Such an enumeration effectively covers the entirety of the individual's conscious activity — at minimum because their sensors are permanently engaged. Given such a comprehensive impact on the psyche, it is logical to observe the reflection of information overload at the behavioral level as well.

At the personal level, the situation is exceptionally complex. Even if one takes only a single subdivision of the ocean of information sources — social networks — researchers find therein alarming evidence of the multidimensional consequences of excessive information uptake through them, reaching the level of mass addiction: 'In addition to the negative impact of social media addiction on users' mental and physical health, social media addiction can also lead to other problems. For example, social media addiction can lead to financial problems... People who are addicted to social media tend to spend more money than those who are not addicted to social media... Students who are addicted to social media are more likely to have lower grades than those who are not addicted to social media' [19].

Mental health; physical health; financial well-being; educational level; personal relationships — the entire complex of the individual's presences in the different dimensions of existence

proves vulnerable to the effect of information overload. The additional problem that complicates it is that the individual is prone to self-induce, replicate, and multiply — personally and volitionally — a 'hunger' for producing, disseminating, and consuming ever more information. The eventual result of 'sticking' to social networks is more than disturbing: 'Social media addicts are unable to detach from them, despite being aware of their destructive effect, and may experience anxiety if they stop using them' [20]. Objectively speaking, this amounts to the individual's self-involvement in voluntary slavery to the ever heavier chains of excessive information, which truly begins to exert upon them an influence similar to that of narcotics: a desire for ever more — and an inability to detach from this opiate.

As with the use of narcotic and stimulating substances, however, the pleasure is temporary while the adverse consequences are lasting. The conclusions from existing research unambiguously impose the following finding: 'Social media addicts are more likely to experience various negative feelings such as depression, anxiety, and loneliness than non-social media addicts... Since time is a constant, this (addiction) has consequences for the time spent in activities other than social media time; thus, social media addiction may also affect the home environment. Therefore, family/interpersonal conflicts may be a potential consequence of social media addiction' [21].

It would be illogical, however, to assume that every human individual uncritically strives for the intoxication of information addiction. The concern of researchers, generated by their observations of the troubling aspects of information overload on the psychology and behavior of people, is accompanied by the self-awareness of the individual themselves of the fact that 'gorging' on information is unfavorable for them. Since it is obvious that human beings have already exceeded all healthy limits for taking in information, it is natural for them to seek — or through evolution to develop — mechanisms through which to limit its harmful effects and benefit from the positives it brings.

The awareness of the gravity of the problem is now manifesting not only at the personal level or in the sphere of scientific research and analysis. It has spread to the 'organizational' level, becoming the subject of discussion, assessment, and resolution by the state, through its legislative and executive power. In November 2024, for the first time, the legislative body of a state — the Parliament of Australia — passed a law prohibiting children under the age of 16 from accessing social networks [22]. Observers point to a number of difficulties in implementing the law in practice. For their part, the companies owning the largest social networks advertise their objections — noting not only the technical difficulties of implementing the adopted measures and certain ambiguities in their application, but also the possible fines of tens of millions of US dollars that hang over them for each registered violation. Whether and to what extent there will be legal disputes over this law is not so important: what is essential is that for the first time at the state level it is acknowledged that abundant information and unceasing communication can also have their 'dark' side. And that — also for the first time — all the institutions of a state, in synchrony (but also following consultations with parents and children), have undertaken active steps to free at least the most vulnerable part of the population from the burden of information. The arguments for these actions are stated in their most concise form in the position of the Prime Minister of Australia: 'Social media is doing social harm to our children. And we have put a stop to it' [23].

The Desire for 'Digital Detoxification'

The individual's awareness of the excessive informational burden falling upon them has led to an unforeseen turning point in their use of the very communication instruments they most frequently employ. In 2024, a startling trend of change in interest in types of devices was registered — this trend can literally be described as the Renaissance of 'grandma's phones,' increasingly replacing smartphones. In Spain alone, sales of basic telephones (also called 'bricks' or 'button phones') have increased by as much as 215%, and according to a study by the company SPC, over 12% of young Spaniards have already switched to such a basic

telephone, with every fifth of them declaring they know someone who is 'offline' because they already have a 'brick' in their hand [24]. In fact, one of the most significant facts is that this trend is being 'fueled' by young people — most notably Generation Z, born between 1995 and 2010 — who have never known a world without Wi-Fi. Why is the 'brick' no longer associated with elderly, visually impaired people lacking sufficient technological experience, but is increasingly being sought by the young? The head of the cited study, Irene Manterola, Marketing Director of SPC, offers a clear answer: 'This is like a digital detox. Our research reveals how young people yearn for simplicity and cut screen time in a world that is online 24/7.'

The growing desire for 'digital detoxification' is becoming visible in more and more regions. Identical trends are shared by observers in the United Kingdom, as Lauren Davis from communications company bOnline notes in a piece titled 'Yes, Dumb Phones are Making a Comeback in 2024... But Why?': 'Switching off from the technology, screens and devices that keep us addicted is becoming increasingly important for people in the United Kingdom and even globally. The benefits of removing constant screen exposure are well-documented and more people than ever are seeking to take advantage of these and enjoy the health and mental health benefits' [25].

It seems almost paradoxical that precisely young people — who are in principle a symbol of passion for the modern, the innovative, the progressive — would reach for 'dumb' phones. To apparently contradict their own essence, they have evidently found a very powerful argument driving them to demonstrate a different type of preference and behavior.

A growing number of experts share the view that the problem cannot be solved by placing barriers, by rationalism in the use of information, or by creating methods for efficiently handling it: 'Nevertheless, whatever information and communication technology tools or techniques you apply, ultimately coping with information overload depends greatly on personal information management capabilities — the way one copes with information search and retrieval processes' [26]. What imposes itself as a conclusion from such a finding once again refers us to the thesis that the way to cope with the information flood is most relevantly to be sought in the individual's own personality, in their leading traits, their capacities, their own psychology.

Researchers have thoroughly and in detail analyzed the possible relevant volitional behavior of the individual under conditions of informational pressure. Concepts such as 'Digital Minimalism' were directly introduced, the definition of which, according to its author, is: 'A philosophy of using technology where you focus your time online on a small number of carefully selected and optimized activities that strongly support the things you value, and then happily skip everything else' [27]. Of utmost importance is the fact that here the author focuses the beam of attention not on the purely utilitarian side of the process of perceiving and processing information (the direct, material benefit from it), but on the values that the individual shares — that is, on the basic traits of their human essence. This is essentially a prioritization of the psychology of the personality in its interaction with the information field.

By introducing the concept of 'digital minimalists,' Newport indirectly poses a current sociological problem: that alongside all the stratification models and schemes of macro-group affiliations formulated until now — estates, classes, status groups, religiosity/atheism — a new sign of division appears and therefore a new sign of grouping. De facto, he outlines the presence of two clearly differentiated groups in society according to the principles by which they consume information. From the term 'digital minimalists' it automatically follows that there also exists its opposite pole: 'digital maximalists,' which we can derive indirectly from the first. Newport does not commit to an assessment of the size of these groups, but in all cases they are supra-class, supra-national, supra-status. When we speak of the presence of these two groups in society — we actually mean a division of civilization as a whole, since this division recognizes no borders, races, nationalities, gender, or age.

From existing data from authoritative surveys, it is visible that 'digital maximalists' more frequently have psychological and health problems, more frequently reduce their financial resources (directly harming their well-being), and achieve lesser success in education and

science. We are only at the beginning of the process of formation of these groups (only 30 years have elapsed since the creation of the World Wide Web), but if the trends registered so far continue — and they are likely to deepen — inevitably these two groups, 'digital minimalists' and 'digital maximalists,' will acquire distinctly constructed features, and it is possible that tension will arise between them. The reasons will be clearly visible: one group will feel less valued, neglected, of lower status, with less access to goods and power, with a lower level of psychological comfort. The opposite state of the other will inevitably give it an evolutionary advantage, and following the natural course of processes, it is likely that it — 'moving in the shadows,' without advertising itself as any structure, without raising slogans, and without personally elevating its own leaders — will begin to dominate society.

The natural aspiration of the average human individual is to reach a better state — be it material and/or psychological. This is why a number of researchers and analysts suggest that through personal volitional efforts, the individual would be inclined to take measures not to fall into the 'B' group. With the aim of encouraging such volitional efforts, they systematize existing experience and develop their own constructions of proposals for how the individual can limit the information they consume to a reasonable level. However, the individual cannot stand in a waiting position for someone to serve them a scientifically grounded and practically tested working scheme of principles through which they can most efficiently and rationally consume information. Therefore, it is logical to assume that individuals themselves create their own defense mechanisms against the information that drowns them.

Conclusion

The birth of the information-saturated era placed the individual in a new communicative environment never before experienced by consciousness. There are no signs whatsoever that the informational pressure on the individual will diminish: on the contrary — this pressure is more likely to increase. Over time, it is very possible that each individual will expand their ability to receive and process larger packages of information. However, this is unlikely to lead to a fundamental change in the situation, since in all cases, always, the quantity of information reaching an individual will exceed their personal capacities to receive and process it.

To cope with the challenge of the avalanche of information fragments, the individual had to develop mechanisms with which to protect themselves from 'overheating' in attempts to receive and process this information. Into such mechanisms were transformed what can be conditionally called the 'valves' of the channels through which communication flows to their consciousness. These valves block the path of that portion of information directed at them which exceeds their capacities to receive and process, or which seems to them irritating, annoying — which they do not perceive as information corresponding to their basic traits as a personality.

Not all individuals, however, will 'switch' these valves on or off in the same way. Observations to date clearly show that two large groups are beginning to form in society, depending on the degree to which they exercise some control over the ubiquitous information that floods every individual without exception. Since the automated reaction of control is subordinated to the personal psychographic profile and is unchangeable in the short term, the volitional reaction may prove decisive for individual well-being — and from there, for the possible new principles of stratification of society.

This paper raises a question that goes beyond the sociology of communication: the gradual emergence of a new stratification axis — one defined not by class, education, or income, but by the psychographic capacity of the individual to filter, regulate, and selectively engage with the information environment. This axis may constitute one of the defining social divisions of the coming decades.

Notes

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Rossen Koutelov is Doctor of Sociology (UNWE Sofia, 2025) and founder of Progress Consult (est. 1996), a Bulgarian marketing research and consulting agency. His doctoral dissertation, 'Psychographic Profiles and Consumer Behavior,' developed an original longitudinal methodology for psychographic segmentation of users, validated through 13 nationally representative surveys (N=12,904, Bulgaria 2013-2023). The methodology identifies four stable psychographic groups — Seekers, Members, Solitary, and Bearings — that determine how individuals filter information in conditions of information overload.

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